

WP3: Task 3.2

Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection

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Introduction

- **Futures** generally involves identifying areas of uncertainty, challenges, underlying drivers and opportunities. In other words, futures is about a structured manner to explore possible and preferable futures.
- **Foresight** is a process to conduct futures work and horizon scanning is a specific technique.
- **Horizon scanning** is a specific foresight methodology that utilizes various steps to identify issues at the edge of current thinking that may have significant impact in the near-medium term (5 years) to long-term future (5-10 years and (>10 years). Source: FAO, 2014

General horizon scanning challenges

- Bring people together (responsibilities are scattered)
- Collaboration cross-domains
- Acceptance of horizon scanning (also policy makers)
- Time and money
- What are the sources
- How to use the data/results (a.o. early warning/cross-border)
- Use it systematically
- Make it quantitative
- Data quality, consistency between regions and availability.
- Obtain data from rural/difficult to reach areas
- Forecast accuracy

TASK 3.2 Overview

- **A cross sector and multisectoral approach**
- **Deliverable:** D-JIP2-3.4 Inventory and tools for horizon scanning (Due Month 18).
Deliverable report includes: Definitions, outcomes of questionnaire and task 3.2 workshop in Uppsala, summary of various tools and.
- **Extra deliverable:** Horizon scanning pilot exercise 27-29 Nov 2019

Building HS-Experts Team

- Diversity
- Expertise
- Leadership and teamwork skills
- Experiences
- Problem-Solving

Deliverable 18 Month

FOOD SAFETY AND QUALITY PROGRAMME

Horizon Scanning and Foresight

An overview of approaches and possible applications
in Food Safety

- Inventory and literature review
 - Many definitions and HS tools are available
 - In general tools
 - Assemble information sources
 - Assemble analysis teams and assign topics
 - Individual team members examine sources: key themes
 - Collective team clusters issues; examines them in a structured way
- COHESIVE Questionnaire
 - Out of 24 independent responders, 20 answered that there is a need to address challenges about horizon scanning methods in One Health
 - Some examples of challenges includes
 - Intersectoral collaboration and communication
 - Communication and harmonization among different actors
 - Bring people together
 - Collaboration cross domains

Outcome of "stakeholder workshop exercise" 11th of April 2019

"Stakeholder view/feelings" about One Health Horizon scanning	EFSA	ECDC
Think & Feel	Think that it is positive and valuable to do and feel responsibility	Think it is important and strategic but feel that it is difficult
Hear	Many is talking about it, hear information from MS and look into databases	Done elsewhere at other agencies, need to foresee things, formal responsibility and expectations to conduct One Health HS.
See	Media reporting, a lot of informal meeting with experts, information from other stakeholders/MS	Disasters and outbreaks can be avoided, HS reports can be questioned, unofficial reports.
Say & Do	Communicate findings to the public, avoid information failure mandate to act, initiate surveillance.	Communicate findings to the public, have a good system in place but some info may be restricted.
Pain	Collaboration with other sectors is complicated, requires resources, difficult to get sustainability and correct data/competences, uncertainty	Resource intensive, creating wrong conclusions leads to lower credibility, uncertainty.
Gain	Proactiveness, better preparedness, prevent disasters/outbreaks, better credibility	Better preparedness, prevent disasters/outbreaks, better credibility

Outcome of FAO Horizon scanning

- **Globalization of trade**
- **Climate change**
- **New technologies**
- **Scientific progress**
- **Urbanization**
- **Public attention to food**

Food and Agriculture
Organization of the
United Nations

FOOD SAFETY AND QUALITY PROGRAMME

Horizon Scanning and Foresight

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Outcome of Deliverable: One Health Horizon Scanning

Aim: To make an inventory and analysis of horizon scanning tools that would be appropriate for one health issues

COHESIVE Expert team

The horizon scanning tool that has been proposed to be used in the coming COHESIVE task 3.2 work is published by Wintle et al 2017 and Sutherland et al 2011.

Examples of HS outcome biological engineering

Issues most relevant in the near term (< 5 years)

- Artificial photosynthesis and carbon capture for producing biofuels
- Enhanced photosynthesis for agricultural productivity
- New approaches to synthetic gene drives
- Human genome editing
- Accelerating defense agency research in biological engineering

Wintle et al 2017 (<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.30247>)

Examples of HS outcome biological engineering

Issues most relevant in the intermediate term (5-10 years)

- Regenerative medicine: 3D printing body parts and tissue engineering
- Microbiome-based therapies
- Producing vaccines and human therapies in plants
- Manufacturing illegal drugs using engineered organisms
- Reassigning codons as genetic firewalls
- Rise of automated tools for biological design, test and optimisation
- Biology as an information science: Impacts on global governance
- Intersection of information security and bio-automation
- Effects of the Nagoya protocol on biological engineering
- Corporate espionage and biocrime

Examples of HS outcome biological engineering

Issues most relevant in the longer term (>10 years)

- New makers disrupt pharmaceutical markets
- Platform technologies to address emerging disease pandemics
- Challenges to taxonomy-based descriptions and management of biological risk
- Shifting ownership models in biotechnology
- Securing the critical infrastructure needed to deliver the bioeconomy

Horizon scanning workshop – 27 Nov 2019

Aim: Conduct a horizon scanning pilot exercise to identify drivers of change in order to strengthen European One Health

Information security: Open source, open and unclassified data

Time frame: 13:40 – 18:10

Main references: (FAO, 2014), Wintle et al 2017 and Sutherland et al 2011

Goal: Generate a long list and a final one health horizon scanning list

General overview – Towards a HS Tool

Wintle et al 2017 (<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.30247>)

Horizon scanning workshop

- **SCAN, IDENTIFY: One Health Long List**
- Scientific and peer-reviewed publications
- Dissertations, Abstracts, Books
- Conferences, Expert meetings, networks, personalized talk/c...
- Official web-sites (EFSA, ECDC)
- Rapid alert, ProMed, Early detection of weak signals, raw data unpublished raw data, closed networks
- Internet, wikipedia
- Non-governmental organisations
- Media, news
- Social media, fake news

Horizon scanning Long List

- Early detection of signals
- Use of fertilizers
- Raw data, unpublished data
- Digitalisation of public and animal health
- Global Transportations (illegal, longer transports)
- New food – insects
- Natural disasters (draught, fires, flooding, earth quakes)
- Warmer climate
- Unknown threats/AMR
- Use of drugs, vaccines
- Immunity status – Elderly people
- Consumer behaviour, trends
 - New food trends, dog food, pets, feed, feed trends
- New food technologies, prolonged shelf-life
- Wild life (wild boars)
- Migration, emigration, travel, homeless, poverty
- Urbanization, rat population, urban farming
- Water sources
- Governance
- Political instability, Geopolitical instability, security policy

Score Long List to Short List

- Information society, influencers, education level, information providers (M)
- Economy/Funding for R&D, scientific network, innovation, early warning (M)
- Lack of trust, political issue, political instability political will (H)
- Food availability, food safety, food security, food trends, production, transportations, water sources, feed safety (M)
- People behaviour, social economic impact, demographic pattern, elderly people in Europe, immunization status, consumer groups, peoples behaviour on animals, companion animals (Horse) (H)
- New threats, emerging threats, illegal trades, activism/terrorism, migration, trafficking (M)
- Environment/Climate change, wild life, less biodeveristy, inscets, land use, water quality (M)

Horizon scanning workshop

SCORE, INVESTIGATE, DISCUSS, REVISE

- **Political & Decision Maker Behaviour**, political change, political will, lack of trust, political instability (Brexit), geopolitical changes, influences on governance and consequences on funding, decision makers and legal framework (1)
- **People/consumer behaviour**, activism, vegan trends, shift of consumption, raw food (spread of pathogens), food fraud (2)
- **Information society**, desinformation, fake news, lack of education, influencers, false alarms, delay detection (3)
- **Science, R&D and Innovations**, new one health innovations/technologies, R&D collaboration within Europe and outside Europe (4)
- **Market behaviour**, Artificial intelligence, new production trend in agriculture and food production, transportation, marketing PR influences on new food/less meat consumption, insects? Interface between, nutrition, safety, control (5)
- **New threats**, man-made-threats (activism/terrorism) illegal trade and trafficking (feed, pet food (dog food), food, pharmaceutical, drugs animals), customs and new collaboration (6)
- **Environment/Climate changes**, warmer climate, land use, biodiversity, urbanization (7)

Environment and Climate Change

- **Water sources**, lack of water, flooding, water quality, drinking water infrastructure, recreation water, aquaculture, lab capacity, water surveillance
- **Wild life**, changing wild life, wild boars, consumption of wild life meat, lab capacity, wild life surveillance
- **Vectors/Inscets**, introduction of new vectors/inscets, less biodeversity, lab capacity, vector surveillance
- **Farmed animals/plants**, regional changes, animal/plant surveillance
- Public health?

Drivers of change – One Health Europe

- **SCORE, INVESTIGATE, DISCUSS, REVISE**
- **Political & Decision Maker Behaviour (1)**
(Top down – Popular science, Conferences for Decision makers, A COHESIVE-partners should contact the Commission/Executive Summary?Final Report?/Dissemination Conference?)
- **People/consumer behaviour (1)/Information society, (3)**
(Education/Influencers/YouTube- New channels, Outreach to children Engagement of NGO:s based on science, One Health Aid,)
- **Science, R&D and Innovations (4)** – Outreach to all stakeholders, Long term One Health Agenda/Framework (linked to political behaviour)
- **Market behaviour, (5)** (Control measures, anti-corruption)
- **New and re-emerging threats/risks, (6)** (Surveillance, Science, Predictive models, Adaptability, Education of local "One Health Teams" – Learning by doing)
- **Environment/Climate changes, (7)** (Education, Awareness, Joint Awareness Mechanisms (Water, Wild Life, Vector), Roles and responsibilities)

Horizon Scanning – Drivers of Change – Dependencies - One Health Flower

Road-map for the horizon scanning work

- 24 month reporting deadline, 9 of December 2019
- Abstract Due 15 of January – One Health Conference in Edinburgh, 18 of June
- 24 month reporting deadline
- ASM-meeting Prague, End of May
- Extra Deliverable?
- Manuscript – Building relationship/network about One Health Foresight/HS (Czech Republic, Germany, Sweden, Italy)

Thank you for your
attention!

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